

Node Name	Min Age	Q1	Median Age	Mean Age	Q3	Max Age	Variance	SD
n257	22.4922461	28.3308351	35.0195851	34.0041747	40.5051139	43.0587563	6.951043e+01	8.337291261
n258	21.7398085	21.7398085	21.7398085	21.7398085	21.7398085	21.7398085	NA	NA
n259	10.6957998	19.4987850	20.9992411	22.5521354	24.8109359	40.3552933	6.196330e+01	7.871676844
n260	14.3336515	15.1266340	16.9499603	20.1348914	17.8493180	34.6833663	6.965831e+01	8.346155338
n261	13.8254294	17.3500521	20.8746749	18.9000348	21.4373374	22.0000000	1.963030e+01	4.430609873
n262	8.2674570	12.9942327	13.3766918	17.1809206	19.7085900	44.2958603	1.201132e+02	10.959617046
n263	11.6676580	11.9166862	13.7253610	18.3018211	18.2685746	42.3492073	1.215023e+02	11.022806779
n264	11.3074645	11.6411873	12.7840747	17.2544161	13.6774289	41.4154443	1.411443e+02	11.880415266
n265	11.0467304	11.1243986	11.3445148	18.3814487	18.6015648	39.7900348	2.037460e+02	14.273962041
n266	10.8823208	10.9826962	11.1967141	18.1343797	18.3483977	39.2617699	1.984289e+02	14.086477980
n267	5.7738060	5.9827515	6.0261000	9.2429048	6.0261040	22.4057625	5.415493e+01	7.359003149
n268	10.6775303	10.7242787	10.8657943	15.4566849	11.0696627	38.5162645	1.276461e+02	11.298059475
n269	7.1433202	7.9864380	8.4893522	11.3687348	8.6779130	30.6197691	7.236208e+01	8.506590153
n270	7.9299083	8.0911383	8.2523682	14.9318196	18.4327753	28.6131824	1.404108e+02	11.849504652
n271	6.6427435	6.8390883	7.3322468	10.2785734	7.5080840	26.1228047	6.038528e+01	7.770796804
n272	6.1123530	6.4730706	6.8337881	12.5423463	15.7373429	24.6808977	1.106384e+02	10.518480889
n273	5.5318420	5.6833590	5.7899205	8.6281640	6.2423575	19.9933411	4.044325e+01	6.359500683
n274	5.3809230	5.5853838	5.8298120	7.7352529	6.0160288	19.7332102	2.805236e+01	5.296447891
n275	3.4184700	3.7210793	3.8219495	3.7290430	3.8299133	3.8538030	4.309463e-02	0.207592454
n276	2.2243040	2.4150750	2.5820770	3.4248889	2.6077595	9.1221722	6.334873e+00	2.516917323
n277	3.8092620	4.2588651	4.2842073	6.1297245	4.4683045	15.6205824	2.167229e+01	4.655351214
n278	0.1526050	0.1706170	1.4824100	2.7078835	2.8861148	10.0425071	1.465053e+01	3.827601636
n279	0.1680660	0.1879020	0.4853190	0.5679572	0.5357770	1.8749574	3.610337e-01	0.600860835
n280	3.4483380	3.5305280	3.6127180	6.5136472	8.0463018	12.4798856	2.670376e+01	5.167567689
n281	2.4430780	2.6000780	2.7193950	3.5724223	2.9752185	8.6938904	5.140696e+00	2.267310259
n282	7.5082385	8.3697974	8.4401100	11.2226005	8.9164799	30.6687844	6.197376e+01	7.872341292
n283	5.8317240	6.4987639	6.5200370	8.8856028	6.6583505	23.5332301	4.180233e+01	6.465472280
n284	3.4274700	3.7384500	3.8320100	5.0932213	3.8501610	13.2158472	1.285324e+01	3.585141636
n285	0.4196550	0.4296950	0.4397350	0.7955567	0.9835076	1.5272802	4.016652e-01	0.633770635
n286	10.1187688	11.4491148	10.7012298	16.8790191	13.6535585	40.7510339	1.386228e+02	11.773819838
n287	12.3367949	12.3376283	12.3384617	12.3384617	12.3392951	12.3401285	5.556454e-06	0.002357213
n288	10.5304438	11.2095374	14.5872601	16.8895312	18.0378600	38.1656654	7.405778e+01	8.605682847
n289	10.0136627	10.2731275	10.6297969	12.0463515	14.6389300	14.6762402	5.730138e+00	2.393770654
n290	6.9794359	8.1625350	11.6644360	11.1075354	14.1800830	14.4236400	1.080151e+01	3.286565213
n291	6.3225445	6.7594660	9.4206630	9.1343196	11.5144940	11.6491100	6.174613e+00	2.484876938
n292	2.3548040	2.7311138	3.6064205	3.3985392	4.0769365	4.1504700	6.397417e-01	0.799838568
n293	4.5800958	5.2886520	7.0053400	6.8776178	8.6590715	8.6624420	3.321884e+00	1.822603506
n294	4.1787990	5.1289133	6.2581125	5.7937331	6.6097345	6.6220000	1.034429e+00	1.017068728
n295	3.8634520	3.9275823	3.9917125	3.9917125	4.0558428	4.1199730	3.290151e-02	0.181387739
n296	7.3844932	7.9588171	10.3269032	10.2795400	12.7697076	12.7883343	6.333546e+00	2.516653743
n297	4.9521150	6.2403953	9.1851225	8.6397538	11.2511962	11.3578560	7.757092e+00	2.785155592
n298	5.5851610	5.9154510	6.2457410	6.2457410	6.5760310	6.9063210	8.727319e-01	0.934201195
n299	2.1957830	2.2987040	2.7709670	2.9264263	3.3868893	3.9679880	6.635455e-01	0.826768107
n300	4.3913853	5.6151566	6.8389280	6.9201044	8.1844640	9.5300000	6.806283e+00	2.527668969
n301	4.5936013	5.3303791	7.4300749	6.8253582	8.2159191	8.3900503	3.013068e+00	1.735819148
n302	4.1722035	4.2438610	4.3155185	4.3155185	4.3871760	4.4588335	4.107838e-02	0.202678017
n303	2.7293880	3.0636078	3.6111525	3.5409692	3.7936123	4.5585970	4.402972e-01	0.663548926
n304	3.9059560	4.4762974	6.0724853	5.6097295	6.7147436	6.7343860	1.749722e+00	1.322770739
n305	3.4997120	3.9591913	5.0692245	4.8096333	5.6816643	5.7446480	1.024547e+00	1.012199088
n306	1.5799340	1.7582140	2.0683305	2.0120555	2.1878660	2.4731850	1.128194e-01	0.335886015
n307	2.6891060	3.1978420	3.7704640	3.7481452	4.3678785	4.6460055	5.876274e-01	0.766568573
n308	2.8294780	3.2528065	3.4463515	3.3052428	3.4987878	3.4987900	1.030450e-01	0.321006208
n309	1.6036030	1.6306588	1.6577145	1.6577145	1.6847703	1.7118260	5.856109e-03	0.076525217
n310	0.4871060	0.4951133	0.5031205	0.5031205	0.5111278	0.5191350	5.129284e-04	0.022647923
n311	3.6532999	7.9414692	18.4347739	14.6797389	18.5969520	21.9999770	5.554413e+01	7.452793385
n312	3.0969730	4.0047720	4.9125710	4.9125710	5.8203700	6.7281690	6.592792e+00	2.567643315
n313	0.6191110	2.2175475	4.8227280	3.6045113	4.9784123	4.9830400	4.119455e+00	2.029644004
n314	2.7181595	3.5206588	4.3231580	4.3231580	5.1256573	5.9281565	5.152040e+00	2.269810646
n315	0.0179270	0.2055643	0.1712150	0.5224277	0.7396370	0.9000840	1.503114e-01	0.387700119
n316	13.2094277	14.6894373	16.1694469	16.1210393	17.5768451	18.9842434	8.338881e+00	2.887712148
n317	11.8365885	11.9751162	12.2007247	12.8140338	13.0396423	15.0180974	2.209995e+00	1.486605063
n318	9.4190176	10.6757340	10.6757405	10.5686663	10.9944380	11.0784013	4.464330e-01	0.668156385
n319	4.2830280	4.8529163	5.0614500	4.9094000	5.1179338	5.2316720	1.810431e-01	0.425491595
n320	6.9250485	7.2321927	7.5393369	7.5393369	7.8464812	8.1536254	7.547006e-01	0.868735040
n321	2.8291110	2.9538207	3.0785304	3.0785304	3.2032401	3.3279498	1.244201e-01	0.352732322
n322	2.6272780	2.7459529	2.8646278	2.8646278	2.9833026	3.1019775	1.126698e-01	0.335663235
n323	2.4000180	2.5057123	2.6114065	2.6114065	2.7171008	2.8227950	8.937020e-02	0.298948484
n324	11.8826648	11.8826648	11.8826648	11.8826648	11.8826648	11.8826648	NA	NA
n325	9.8622455	11.0682280	11.3986431	13.6433549	12.5133867	22.6332555	2.666495e+01	5.163811676
n326	9.4964128	9.9266021	10.3567914	10.3567914	10.7869807	11.2171701	1.480503e+00	1.216759161
n327	6.9919767	7.9814300	11.5091574	11.1793396	14.7070670	14.7070670	1.688323e+01	4.108920366
n328	4.4424450	4.8402684	5.2070772	5.1885988	5.5842609	5.8470060	2.881811e-01	0.536825063
n329	3.7009810	4.2364910	4.9976954	5.8075639	8.0513260	8.0513260	4.407696e+00	2.099451436
n330	4.0049850	4.4009303	4.7968755	4.7639842	5.1434838	5.4900920	5.521971e-01	0.743099644
n331	2.3740030	2.9874095	3.3108200	3.1104665	3.3519825	3.4096585	1.441125e-01	0.379621513
n332	2.4262040	2.5472593	2.6683145	2.6683145	2.7893698	2.9104250	1.172350e-01	0.342395953
n333	3.0672930	3.3536390	3.4537530	3.6368540	3.6473070	4.6622780	3.724350e-01	0.610274547
n334	3.3174200	3.4785386	3.6396573	3.6396573	3.8007759	3.9618945	2.076737e-01	0.455712289
n335	2.9082070	3.0375515	3.1668960	3.1668960	3.2962405	3.4255850	1.338400e-01	0.365841492
n336	6.4901043	6.7548642	7.0196240	7.0782358	7.3723016	7.7249792	3.838055e-01	0.619520358
n337	5.1643530	5.8660845	6.2267450	6.0402515	6.4009120	6.5431630	3.739363e-01	0.611503321
n338	5.6971505	6.2073208	6.4725678	6.3598579	6.6251049	6.7971455	2.246436e-01	0.473965868
n339	3.3141840	3.7310860	3.7967050	4.8443528	5.0251008	8.2226890	4.382251e+00	2.093382637
n340	6.5713000	7.8478863	7.9214353	7.7422748	7.9793078	8.2175098	3.468375e-01	0.588929123
n341	4.9286330	5.6698280	5.6862690	5.6246557	5.8135810	5.9263970	1.276384e-01	0.357265112
n342	4.5179220	5.0945168	5.3404645	5.1608469	5.4067947	5.4445368	1.880451e-01	0.433641688
n343	3.9094410	4.3257480	4.5311558	4.4066016	4.6120094	4.6546540	1.162025e-01	0.340884914
n344	8.5866236	9.4071402	10.2276568	10.0089100	10.7200532	11.2124495	1.759628e+00	1.326509731
n345	6.9820981	7.6624323	8.3427665	8.4206529	9.1399303	9.9370941	2.187550e+00	1.479036866
n346	6.2848971	7.2289350	7.4579823	9.0258784	8.2550814	15.5567620	1.212785e+01	3.482505886
n347	5.7308092	6.2519884	6.3827302	6.3529669	6.5256355	6.8398533	1.390683e-01	0.372918563
n348	5.0843193	5.7024969	6.0309493	6.0592220	6.3876744	7.0906700	6.819597e-01	0.825808506
n349	4.1320500	4.7315119	4.9254013	4.7752658	4.9284171	5.0724380	1.165261e-01	0.341359125
n350	0.5650320	1.4501485	1.9739585	2.3049306	2.7134388	4.7551030	2.619991e+00	1.618638543
n351	3.1757560							